

Optimizing Yield Through Machine Intelligence

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Abstract—Agriculture employs about three-quarter of Nigeria's workforce and yet food sufficiency is a challenge in the country. This is largely due to poor and outdated pre-harvest and post-harvest farming practices. The land fallow system is still been practised as fertiliser production in the country is grossly inadequate and expensive. The few available post-harvest processing facilities are faced with ageing and are inefficient. Also, use of modern processing equipment is limited by farmers' lack of fund, adequate capacity to operate and maintain modern farming equipment. This paper, therefore, examines key barriers to agricultural products processing equipment in the country. These barriers include over-dependence on foreign technologies and expertise; poor and inadequate manufacturing infrastructure; and lack of political will by political leaders; lack of funds; and lack of adequate technical skills. This paper, however, sees the increase in the domestic manufacturing of pre-harvest and post-harvest machinery and equipment through reverse engineering approach as a key to food production sufficiency in Nigeria.

I. INTRODUCTION

AGRICULTURE is a key to accelerated economic growth and an enhanced standard of living of the citizenry. This sector has a lot of challenges in developing countries of Africa with Nigeria inclusive. Food insufficiency is a common trait to countries of Africa and a major issue in Nigeria. Globally, agricultural sector is a priority in national planning and national annual budget as food sufficiency is a measure of the economic development of a given country [1].

Despite the fact that Nigeria is massively endowed with agricultural resources, the country's agricultural sector has been growing at a very low rate. Less than 50% of cultivable agricultural land in the country is cultivated. The greater part of the cultivated land is based on smallholder and farmers use of traditional and rudimentary production techniques which lowers yields [1]. In addition, the farming system is monotonous, boring and uninteresting. The slow growth of food production results in growing food insecurity and food imports. Most households in Nigeria spend up to 70% of their income on food and yet close to 50% of the children less than five years are malnourished [2]. The amount of the total food

imported into the country from 1990–2011 was about 74,487.37 USD and the average food imported per day was put at about 9.28

USD [3]. Nigeria imported agricultural produce worth of N630 billion in 2012 and the country is ranked number one importer of rice globally, former Nigeria President, Goodluck Jonathan revealed [4]. Apart from rice importation, wheat, sugar, fish and poultry products are equally imported to Nigeria massively.

II. AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IMPEDING FACTORS

The barriers that impede the growth of agricultural production in this country can be classified into technological constraints, environmental, sociocultural and socio-political barriers.

A. Technological Constraints

Use of Traditional Method

The structure and methods of production for the past four decades (over 40 years of independence) have relatively remained the same. Over 90% of Nigerian farmers still depend on cutlasses, holes and sticks for pre-harvest operations and sell their farm produce without post-harvest process [5], [6]. This is the foremost barrier to agricultural sector growth. The farming population is made up of small-scale, subsistence peasants, farming on an average about two hectares of land and usually on scattered holdings. Farming activities are also carried out mainly with traditional, rudimentary technology consisting mainly of hoes and cutlasses, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
ESTIMATES OF AREAS UNDER DIFFERENT POWER SOURCES IN NORTHERN STATES OF NIGERIA [5]

	Power sources		
	Hoe	Animal	Tractor
Number of farmers (million)	7.5	0.1	0.015
Size of land cultivated (ha/farmer/yr)	1.0	5.0	50.0
Annual total area cultivated (million ha)	7.5	0.5	0.75
Total area percentage (%)	86.0	5.5	8.5

Poor Storage Facilities

Presently, the available storage technology is grossly inadequate and not complimenting the efforts of the small holders to carter for their produce during season. The annual crop loss is about 20% of the harvest and this is a huge loss. This challenge should be of concern to all the stakeholders in the sector; from research scientists, engineers to the extension workers in the field

to the farmers on the farm and to the government policy formulators [7].

Poor Post Process Facilities

A wide range of agricultural products found in formal markets requires post-harvest processing and this makes processing facilities equipment relevant in agricultural sector. Consequently, this creates a lot of business opportunities for local manufacturers of agro-allied processing machines (both "pre" and "post" harvest machinery). Domestic agricultural equipment production is pivotal to food sufficiency production and national food security [8]. Every region in Nigeria is blessed with different economic endowments such as cultivable soil, solid minerals, and crude oil. These endowments remain economically useless (with exception of few) if additional values in form of post-harvest operation are not added. Capacity constraint in manufacturing, due to poor infrastructure, is a key limiting factor threatening agricultural growth and food security in Nigeria. The endowments become less economical and worthless, in some cases they are taken away cheaply when there is insufficient post-process operation. The discovery of crude oil in Nigeria contributed to the dwindling and abandoning of agriculture sector by many people [9].

B. Sociocultural and Socio-Political Barriers

Non-Involvement of Elites

The small-scale farmers' low level of education, particularly women who form the majority of the agricultural labour force has remained a major challenge to the adoption of modern farming techniques and the ability to access other inputs necessary for increase productivity in the sector. Inadequate Government Policy and Lack of Government

Political Will

Nigeria returned to democracy in 1999 and the government then itemised various factors that are hindering national economic growth. These barriers include mono-economy (reliance on only oil), inadequate manufacturing infrastructure, agricultural neglect and over dependence on foreign products [8]. As a result, the government came up with a policy to make the development of agriculture a priority to tackle poverty, improve standard of living and boost the economy. In this policy, there were plans for new technology, improved seedlings, better storage facilities and access to funds at reduced lending rates. Also, it was reported that the government would diversify the economy, move the country away from mono-economy and an import dependent country. Subsequently, there were plans of incentives and encouragement for agro-allied industries development under small and medium-scale enterprises (SME) act [10], [11]. However, the same government failed to show sincere commitment in the policy implementation. Consequently, billions of naira was reportedly spent and insignificant achievement was recorded.